

2 (B) (a) *Spirodela polyrhiza* (L.) Schleid.

2 (C) *Allium schoenoprasum* L.

(a) cv. Nelly

2 (D) *Secale cereal* L. cv. Dukato

2 (F)

Taraxacum officinale L.
- wild population Dittelbrunn.

**2 (G) *Myosotis sylvatica* EHRH. EX HOFFM.
cv. Heavenly Blue**

2 (H)*Beta vulgaris* subsp. *vulgaris*
CONDITIVA group L.

2 (I)

Cucumis sativus L.
cv. Vorgebirgstraupe

2 (J) (a) *Valerianella carinata* LOISEL.

2 (K)*Vaccinium myrtillus* L.**(a)**

2 (L) (a) *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.

2 (M) *Centaureum erythraea* RAFN.

2 (N)

Pelargonium zonale (L.) L'Hér.

2 (O) (a) *Digitalis purpurea* L.

2 (P) (a)

Plantago major L. -
wild population Dittelbrunn

2 (Q) *Linum usitatissimum* L.

2 (S)

(a) *Oenothera speciosa* NUTT.

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

2 (U) (a) *Fragaria vesca* L. cv. Rügen

2 (V) (a) *Ruta graveolens* L.

2 (W) (a) *Solanum lycopersicum* L.
cv. Harzfeuer

□ MS
▨ DMSO
■ 0.03 mM progesterone
■ 0.03 mM testosterone

Supporting information Figure S3: Seedling and root morphology of progesterone- or testosterone-treated non-Brassicales angiosperms. The figure depicts the morphology of seedlings and roots of the following *Brassicacea* species: **(A)** *Nymphaea colorata* PETER., **(B)** *Spirodela polyrhiza* (L.) SCHLEID., **(C)** *Allium schoenoprasum* L. cv. Nelly, **(D)** *Secale cereal* L. cv. Dukato, **(E)** *Petroselinum crispum* (MILL.) FUSS cv. Mooskrause, **(F)** *Taraxacum officinale* L. – wild population Dittelbrunn, **(G)** *Myosotis sylvatica* EHRH. EX HOFFM. cv. Heavenly Blue, **(H)** *Beta vulgaris* subsp. *vulgaris* CONDITIVA group L., **(I)** *Cucumis sativus* L. cv. Vorgebirgstraube, **(J)** *Valerianella carinata* LOISEL., **(K)** *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., **(L)** *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L., **(M)** *Centaurium erythraea* RAFN., **(N)** *Pelargonium zonale* (L.) L'Hér., **(O)** *Digitalis purpurea* L., **(P)** *Plantago major* L. – wild population Dittelbrunn, **(Q)** *Linum usitatissimum* L., **(R)** *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., **(S)** *Oenothera speciosa* NUTT., **(T)** *Papaver rhoeas* L., **(U)** *Fragaria vesca* L. cv. Rügen, **(V)** *Ruta graveolens* L. **(W)** *Solanum lycopersicum* L. cv. Harzfeuer (a) gives the root lengths of the analyzed plant as mean \pm SEM. Statistical differences, indicated by asterisks (* = $p \leq 0.05$; ** = $p \leq 0.01$; *** = $p \leq 0.001$), were determined by one-way ANOVA and Turkey test. (b – e) are pictures of the morphology of the seedlings. (f – h) show microscopic pictures of the root tips of the analyzed plant. b and f = MS control; c and g = DMSO mock treatment; d and h = 30 μ M progesterone; e and h = 30 μ M testosterone. Green arrows indicate uncoordinated cell growth, while white arrows indicate enhanced root hair development.